

Panorama 2022/23

The Swiss Academy
of Engineering Sciences:
Review and Outlook

Review and Outlook

Benoît Dubuis and Esther Koller

For how long have people been saying that the next ten years will be crucial in a world being transformed by the effects of technology?

Forever – and they will keep saying it forever because technological development has become autocatalytic, particularly because the applications of technology broke through sectoral boundaries a long time ago. Blockchain was developed for the world of finance, but is being used in medicine; drones were developed for surveillance, but are assisting farmers; AI for search engines, but we encounter it in everyday life, taking the place of the people we usually talk to in information services.

Should we be concerned at this surreptitious and insidious intrusion of technology into the very heart of our lives? While we prefer to see opportunities that will help us in our tasks and lives, these advances nevertheless deserve our attention so that we can ensure technology is integrated in a way that has been carefully thought through and shows concern and respect for humans, social cohesion and the Earth that is our shared home.

SATW is committed to investing in a new generation of professionals qualified to support technological development, to the social and economic advancement of our country by safeguarding the development and availability of technology and controlling its impact on our society and environment.

To do this, SATW operates an impressive network of experts, who share their expertise, vision, time and networks to further our studies and meetings. As a neutral, independent and global organisation, SATW is dedicated to the service of our society, economy and country, helping position Switzerland in a technological universe that is taking shape with us.

Video message
satw.ch/video-message

2022

As the most important network of experts for the engineering sciences in Switzerland, SATW's goal is to further enhance Switzerland's leading position in this field, and to help ensure that findings are translated into technologies and innovations for the benefit of the economy and society.

01.01.2022
Newly elected Full Members of SATW in 2022

10.02.2022
Publication: Autonomous driving

01.02.2022
New edition of Innovativeness Analysis

28.03.–01.04.2022, Brugg and Lausanne
Swiss Space Week

28.04.2022
Statement: Half-and-half in STEM professions

03.05.2022, Bern
General Meeting elects Benoit Dubuis as SATW's new President

03.05.2022
Consultation response: Mobility data

23.06.2022, Lucerne
Launch of Swiss Artificial Intelligence Research Overview Platform

28.06.2022
White paper: Study on working from home and cyber security

22.07.2022
Study: A technological panorama

05.09.2022, Lausanne
Launch of mentoring programme Swiss TecLadies

28.09.2022
Statement: Further development of the Matura secondary school diploma

29.09.2022, Dübendorf
Technology Days: Electromobility

14.11.–18.11.22, Lausanne and Zurich
Swiss Food Week

14.11.22, Biel
Event: SMEs and digitalisation

2023

01.01.2023
Newly elected Full Members of SATW in 2023

15.09.2023, Zurich
Launch: Technology Outlook

23.09.2023, Lausanne
Conference on encouraging young engineering talent

25.01.–27.01.23, Tenero
Sportech

01.12.2022, Dübendorf
Workshop: Autonomous systems

17.05.2023, Zurich
Annual congress: Security of supply and technical sovereignty

21.02.23
CAETS Energy Report 2022

Online version: [Timeline](https://satw.ch/timeline)
satw.ch/timeline

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- 2 Prof. Christofer Hierold (Vice-President)
- 3 Dr. Rita Hofmann (Vice-President)
- 4 Prof. Peter Seitz (Vice-President)
- 5 Dr. Ulrich Claessen
- 6 Prof. René Hüsler
- 7 Dr. Fabienne Marquis Weible
- 8 Dr. Hans-Peter Meyer

Would you like to contribute your expertise to our projects?
Then we look forward to hearing from you.

satw.ch/contact

Head Office

From left to right: Dr. Christian Holzner, Adriana Cantaluppi, Dr. Claudia Schärer, Elvira Affeltranger, Claude Naville, Sibylle Gerspacher, Esther Lombardini, Belinda Weidmann, Cyrielle Rubrichi, Christina Dall'Agnola, Ester Elices, Stefan Scheidegger, Dr. Esther Koller, Edith Schnapper, Sandra Weidmann, Manuel Kugler, Nicole Wettstein, Manuela Ingleto, Claudia Lambrigger, Beatrice Huber, Alexandre Luyet, Janine Hosp

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- 10 Dr. Xaver Edelmann, Sustainable Circular Economy
- 11 Prof. Giovanni Sansavini, Resilience and Risks
- 12 Prof. Daniel Gygax, Technologies for Precision Medicine

New Members 2023

«I am looking forward to expanding my scientific network and exchanging ideas with other university institutions more intensively.»

Prof. Tanja Zimmermann
Empa

«I greatly appreciate SATW's excellent reputation and its values. My contribution to the interdisciplinary network will focus on knowledge transfer, outreach and inclusion.»

Prof. Robert Riener
ETH Zurich

«There are many technological ideas for solving problems, but society's acceptance of them must always be considered.»

Prof. Christian Franck
ETH Zurich

«I want to contribute to the analysis and dissemination – applying intellectual rigour and weighting – of all information linked to scientific progress.»

Prof. Luc Thévenaz
EPFL

«Through SATW, I hope to contribute to enhancing the cyber security of Switzerland, Europe, and the entire world. It is an honor to be part of this prestigious academy.»

Prof. Adrian Perrig
ETH Zurich

Gion A. Caminada
ETH Zurich

«SATW is a beacon of intellectual strength and positive societal values of Switzerland, and I especially hope to contribute to the visibility and impact of women in technological scientific disciplines in Switzerland and internationally.»

Prof. Olga Sorkine-Hornung
ETH Zurich

Prof. Tobias J. Kippenberg
EPFL

«SATW plays an important role in representing the technological and scientific interests of Switzerland as a nation.»

Christoph Aeschlimann
Swisscom

«I would like to tackle global challenges in cooperation with SATW and other tech enthusiasts from various disciplines.»

Prof. Christian Rüegg
Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI)

«I hope to promote engineering education and research through strengthening Sino-Swiss networking and international exchanges in the framework of SATW.»

Prof. Junguo Liu
North China University of Water Resources and Electric Power

«Technology should serve people and not the other way around.»

Prof. Roger Abächerli
HSLU

More about the new members
satw.ch/new-members